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FINAL REPORT

Benthic Ecological Survey in Coastal Waters of Pwani and Tanga Regions, Tanzania

Final Report on

**Benthic Ecological Survey in
Coastal waters of Pwani and
Tanga Regions**

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Asasi ya Uwezeshaji Tanzania
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Preface

The northern coast of Tanzania Mainland boasts a wealth of vibrant and productive ecosystems, including coral reefs, mangroves, seagrass meadows, and more. These ecosystems are not only havens for diverse marine life, but also important for the livelihoods of coastal communities. Unfortunately, these critical ecosystems face a multitude of threats, ranging from overfishing and destructive fishing practices to pollution and climate change. Recognizing the urgency of protecting these marine jewels, a Benthic Ecological Survey (BES) was conducted along the northern coast of Tanzania Mainland. This survey aimed to gather critical data on the benthic composition of shallow coastal waters (less than 50 meters).

Therefore, this report offers valuable insights obtained from the survey, including:

Detailed of data – learn about the methods employed for data collection, processing, and analysis, providing a transparent and reliable picture of the survey.

Mapping of benthic communities and substrate type – identify areas with significant high and low clusters of benthic communities and substrate types within the shallow coastal waters of Tanzania’s northern coast.

Recommendations for future research – gain valuable insights into potential avenues for further exploration and understanding of the benthic communities and substrate type, both within Tanzania and across the Western Indian Ocean.

This report is the first in the coastal waters of Tanzania to provide comprehensive data of benthic communities and substrate types and the findings presented in this report paves the way for informed and effective marine conservation strategies. It serves as a crucial resource for stakeholders, policymakers, and researchers dedicated to protecting and preserving the invaluable marine ecosystems of Tanzania and beyond.

Mr. Issac Isae
Director
Asasi ya Uwezeshaji Tanzania – ASUTA

Executive Summary

The northern coast of Tanzania Mainland features diverse and productive ecosystems, including critical ones such as mangroves, seagrass meadows, and coral reefs, which support the livelihoods of coastal communities through activities like artisanal fishing and marine tourism. However, these ecosystems are under threat from overfishing, destructive fishing practices, poorly planned coastal development, and climate change. These challenges not only threaten ecosystem health and biodiversity but also pose risks to the livelihoods and food security of coastal communities. Addressing these challenges involves, among others, the development of a management network for Marine Management Areas (MMAs), which, in turn, necessitates comprehensive data and information about benthic ecosystems.

Consequently, a Benthic Ecological Survey (BES) was conducted to gather data and information on the benthic ecosystems along the northern coast of the Tanzania Mainland. A boat-based survey was employed to capture photos of benthic habitats within a 1000-meter-interval grid in the designated study area, focusing on depths below 50 meters. High-quality photos for 2156 grids out of the total 3113 surveyed, constituting around 69 percent of the surveyed grids, were successfully acquired and subsequently uploaded to CoralNet for annotation and analysis. The "Three" replicate accounted for 96.85 percent of the collected data, indicating a prevalent occurrence of triple measurements at the surveyed locations, effectively minimizing sampling bias.

Results show that the northern coast of the "Tanzania Mainland is characterized by diverse substrates, including seagrass meadows, live coral reefs, algae beds, rocky outcrops, rubbles, and extensive sandflats, with varying proportions of these habitats across different spatial locations. Seagrass, algae, and coral reef benthic communities exhibited a depth-dependent pattern that reveals the unique preferences and biological niches of these communities in this particular coastal area. Distinct clusters with notably high and low percentage cover existed along the northern coast of "Tanzania Mainland, signifying hotspots and coldspots of seagrass, corals, and algae. Based on study findings, recommendations have been provided, with a focus on improving the data collection approach in future BES studies in both the "Tanzania Mainland and the Western Indian Ocean (WIO) region.

Abbreviations

BES – Benthic Ecological Survey
CFMAs – Collaborative Fisheries Management Areas
GPS – Global Position System
MMAs – Marine Managed Areas
TACMP – Tanga Coelacanth Marine Park
TMRS — Tanga Marine Reserves System
WIO – Western Indian Ocean

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Genesis

Coastal waters on the northern coast of the Tanzania Mainland support a range of productive ecosystems, such as coral reefs, mangroves, seagrass meadows, rock shores, and muddy flats (Osuka et al. 2021). Critical among these ecosystems are the mangroves, seagrass meadows, and coral reefs, characterized by their high biodiversity, which play a vital role in supporting the livelihoods of coastal communities through activities such as artisanal fishing, mariculture, and marine and coastal tourism (Howe et al. 2022). Unfortunately, these critical ecosystems face threats from overfishing, habitat destruction through the use of destructive fishing gear, inadequately designed infrastructure projects, poorly planned mariculture, and climate change (George 2019). These challenges not only jeopardize the health of ecosystems, including their biodiversity, but also present risks to the livelihoods and food security of coastal communities. Therefore, it becomes crucial to protect and conserve these critical ecosystems to ensure their continued support for current and future generations.

Figure 1.1: Seagrass at at grid number 193

Figure 1.2: Coral reef at grid number 201

Several initiatives have been put in place to protect and conserve marine coastal ecosystems, including the establishment of the Tanga Coelacanth Marine Park (TACMP) and the Tanga Marine Reserves System (TMRS), as well as the formation of Collaborative Fisheries Management Areas (CFMAs) . However, indiscriminate practices continue to degrade these critical coastal ecosystems. This is partly a result of the underdeveloped management network of Ma-

rine Management Areas (MMAs), which is, in turn, attributed to a lack of data and information about these ecosystems, both in space and time. Hence, there is a pressing requirement to generate data and information concerning the critical coastal ecosystems on the northern coast of Tanzania Mainland. This information can facilitate the comprehensive development of Marine Management Areas (MMAs).

1.2 Objectives

In response, a Benthic Ecological Survey (BES) was conducted in the coastal waters of the northern coast of Tanzania Mainland. The objective was to generate comprehensive data on benthic composition in nearshore waters (<50 m) along this coastline. The collected data will facilitate a multi-parametric marine spatial analysis designed to identify optimal areas for establishing no-take replenishment zones. These zones will be instrumental in the development of MMAs.

This report delves into the methods used to gather, process, and analyze data for the Benthic Ecosystem Survey (BES). It then presents important information about the various seabed habitats found in deep waters (less than 50 meters) along the northern coast of mainland Tanzania. The report concludes by offering recommendations for future BES studies, both within Tanzania and throughout the Western Indian Ocean (WIO) region. In essence, this report sheds light on the benthic communities and substrates types found in the shallow coastal waters of Tanzania's northern coast, revealing the diverse habitats that exist. It also suggests ways to improve future studies of this important marine environment, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of benthic ecosystems and substrates.

Figure 1.3: Seagrass and sand at grid 2744

Figure 1.4: Seagrass and sand at grid 2758

Chapter 2

Methods

2.1 Study area

The Benthic Ecological Survey (BES) was implemented along the northern coast of Tanzania, specifically in the coastal waters of four districts — Bagamoyo, Pangani, Tanga, and Mkinga (Figure 2.1). It is noteworthy that, despite the inclusion of the geographical area of Muheza District within the survey area, this specific zone was deliberately excluded from the designated sampling area

Figure 2.1: The map from Bagamoyo to Mking that was sampled for benthic survey.

because is the area where the Tanga Coelacanth Marine Park (TACMP) is situated. To easy sampling during data collection, the area was divided into 3 blocks each with 1000 grids (see Figure 2.1), and four field teams worked concurrently.

2.2 Grids and sampling

The survey area was determined by focusing on coastal waters with a depth below 50 meters. This choice was based on the knowledge that most benthic communities thrive in shallow areas, with their abundance and diversity decreasing significantly beyond 50 meters. Within this depth limit, the entire coastal area was divided into 1 km x 1 km grids (Figure 2.2), resulting in a total of 3,252 grids. This grid system provided a structured framework for the survey and ensured comprehensive coverage of the selected area. The combined area of all 3,252 grids amounted to 3,252 square kilometers.

Within each grid as highlighted in Figure 2.2, three replicate sampling points were designated for detailed study. This approach helped to capture the spatial variability within the grid and provide a more accurate representation of the benthic communities present. At each replicate point, the following data were collected:

1. **Location Information:** Precise coordinates were recorded using GPS technology.
2. **Depth Measurement:** An accurate depth reading was obtained using a specialized instrument.
3. **Photographic Survey:** A camera was lowered to the seabed to capture images of the substrate (the bottom surface) and the various benthic communities inhabiting the area.

Figure 2.2: Conceptual framework of one kilometer grids and replicates. The grey color represent the land, the color coded points with labels (A,B, and C) are replicate in each grid.

The centroid of each grid was computed and its longitude and latitude value extracted. The num-

ber of grids within the area generated were 3251 covering an estimated area of 3251 km². These pre-defined sampling points were uploaded in the LocusMap Application that run Android Operating System in Rugged smart phones. The selection of rugged smartphones is founded on their extended battery life when compared with typical smartphones, their user-friendly nature, and their suitability for operation in sea environments.

2.3 Planning Survey Area for Different Scenarios

To make the sampling process more organized and efficient, we divided the entire survey area into smaller sections called “blocks.” Each block had a different number of grids, which are like smaller squares within each block (Table 2.1). This helped us keep track of where we were sampling and ensure we covered the entire area. We also had to consider the weather conditions during the sampling period, which was during the southeast monsoon season. This season brings strong winds blowing north and the powerful East Africa Coastal Current also flows northwards. To account for these challenging conditions, we planned our sampling for three different scenarios:

1. **Sampling 30 grids per day:** This was our most conservative option, designed for situations where the wind and current were particularly strong.
2. **Sampling 45 grids per day:** This was our middle option, suitable for conditions with moderate wind and current.
3. **Sampling 60 grids per day:** This was our most ambitious option, only possible when the wind and current were calm.

With these different scenarios planned (Table 2.1), we were able to adapt our sampling strategy to the actual weather conditions on each day. This helped us make the most of our time and limited resources while still collecting valuable data.

Table 2.1: The total grids per blocks and the planned number of grid sample per day and the estimated number of days required for each block at three scenarios of grids

Blocks	Grids	Sample Grids per day		
		Grids 30	Grids 45	Grids 60
Block four	526	6	4	3
Block one	885	10	7	5
Block three	777	9	6	4
Block two	916	10	7	5
Total	3104	35	24	17

2.4 Data collection

2.4.1 Tools Used for Benthic Ecological Survey

To ensure the accuracy and completeness of our benthic ecological survey, we used several tools to record ancially information and photos. These tools include:

1. Echosounder: This instrument emitted sound waves beneath the water surface, allowing us to measure the depth of each sampling location. This information is required for understanding the physical environment of the benthic community and its potential impact on the organisms living there.

2. Geographical Position System (GPS) — was used to record geographical location (latitude, longitude) of each sampling site. This information is important for mapping the distribution and abundance of different benthic species across the surveyed area.
3. GoPro Camera—was used to capture images of the benthic ecosystems. This camera are waterproof thus allow to take photographs directly underwater, providing valuable visual data on the composition and diversity of the benthic community. These images enable us to identify and classify different species, document their interactions with the environment, and analyze the overall health and condition of the benthic habitat.

2.4.2 Navigating to grid points

The data collection strategy for a benthic ecological survey conducted in the coastal regions of Tanzania , specifically from Bagamoyo District in the Pwani region to Mkinga District in the Tanga region. The Figure 2.3 illustrate the systematic process, starting with the establishment of one-kilometer grids over the specified geographical range. These grids serve as a framework for organizing and conducting the survey. The centroid points of predefined one-kilometer grids were calculated and their longitude and latitude were converted into points and saved in GPX format. These points were then imported into the LocusMap navigation app on the Android Operating System.

Figure 2.3: The conceptual framework for data collection

In order to navigate to the sampling points, users had to select the unique identification number of the grid, which would generate a path and calculate the Euclidean distance to the selected points. Once at the sampling points, the depth of the area was measured. If the depth was less than 50 meters (Figure 2.3), a Go-Pro camera was lowered to capture underwater images of benthic communities and substrate. The GPS also recorded the geographical information (date, longitude and latitude) of the point. However, if the depth of the selected point was greater than 50 meters (Figure 2.3), only the geographical location was marked without capturing any

images. This process allowed for efficient navigation and data collection during the sampling activities.

2.4.3 Photo Capture

A GoPro11 camera was attached to a 1 meter metal frame with a 100 meter rope for lowering and raising it. The camera was only lowered when the water depth was 50 meters or less (*See* Figure 2.3). Before lowering the camera, it was turned on and set to timelapse mode to capture images every two seconds. The first image captured the sampling station code written on a board. Then, the camera was slowly lowered to the seabed. Once it reached the bottom, the frame was lifted about 20 centimeters above the surface to prevent the boat from drifting and tilting the images. The camera captured images of the bottom for 10-20 seconds, taking between 5 and 10 images depending on the depth. The camera was then immediately raised and turned off.

2.5 Data Processing

2.5.1 Waypoints and depth

After every day of fieldwork, the team meticulously recorded all waypoint information for each replicate. This information included geographic coordinates (longitude and latitude), the unique identifier (ID), the replicate label (A, B, or C), and the measured depth. All of this data was carefully entered into an Excel spreadsheet. Additionally, the waypoints marked with a GPS device were exported and saved in a standard GPX format. This comprehensive data collection ensured accurate planning for subsequent monitoring activities. Notably, a consultant created a helpful Shiny dashboard specifically for this purpose (Figure 2.4), which can be accessed online at <https://semba.shinyapps.io/besa/>. This dashboard utilizes the recorded waypoints to optimize the planning process and enhance the efficiency of future field operations.

Figure 2.4: A screenshot of BES dashboard that was used to plan and monitor the progress of the field survey

2.5.2 Photo Selection

Each day upon returning back from field, the data team transferred collected images from the camera to an external hard drive, organizing them into different folders and subfolders for easy tracking. Later that same day, the data team carefully examined the images to ensure that all

grids had images and that the quality was acceptable. This daily review helped identify any points or replicate that needed to be recaptured due to poor image quality. After reviewing all the images, the team selected high-quality benthic images. The selection criteria were based on image quality and representation of benthic communities and substrates on the images. They chose one image from each replicate (a total of 3 images per grid). These selected images were renamed with the grid and replicate number (e.g., 1422a). Finally, all chosen images were kept in a single folder, ready to be uploaded to CoralNet.

2.5.3 Image Annotation

The underwater images was uploaded in the powerful platform CoralNet (<https://coralnet.ucsd.edu/>), which is capable of analysing benthic images (Lozada-Misa, Schumacher, and Vargas-Ángel 2017). Deep neural networks are used in this platform to facilitate both fully and semi-automated annotation processes, rendering it an efficient tool for image classification. Collaboration among researchers is fostered through its collaborative workspace features, making CoralNet more than a simple data repository. Developed with support from NSF and NOAA (Chen et al. 2021), this open-source and freely accessible platform offers a comprehensive suite of modules, including an interactive image viewing window. Features of interest within selected images can be readily identified by researchers using the interactive window displayed on the CoralNet website. Additionally, valuable numerical data is generated, which can be used for estimating percentage cover (Lamirand et al. 2022), determining the presence or absence of specific habitats, and conducting statistical analyses (Lozada-Misa, Schumacher, and Vargas-Ángel 2017).

2.5.4 Image Classification Procedure

Using CoralNet for image classification involved a standard procedure:

1. **Source Creation** – The first step involved creating a “source” on the CoralNet platform. This essentially meant establishing a centralized hub for managing the benthic survey or image source. The administrator, serving as the command center, could then invite researchers and users to assist with image annotation and manage image access permissions;
2. **Labelset Development** – Next, labelsets to categorize the various benthic features present in the images was created. In this case, 22 distinct labelsets shown in Table 2.2 were created.
3. **Image Upload** – Once the labelsets were established, we proceeded to upload the images. The administrator accessed the upload image section within CoralNet, clicked “choose files,” selected the desired photographs from the stored files, and initiated the upload process.
4. **Image Annotation** – Following the upload, we utilized CoralNet’s annotation tools to assign relevant labelset categories to each image. This process could involve either fully automated or semi-automated methods, depending on the chosen workflow. The interactive image viewing window played a crucial role in this stage, enabling researchers to visually confirm and refine the annotations for each image.
5. **Data Analysis** – With the annotations finalized, we harnessed the power of CoralNet’s data analysis tools. Utilizing the numerical data generated by the platform, we estimated percentage cover for each benthic category, identified the presence or absence of specific habitats within the images, and conducted comprehensive statistical analyses to further refine our understanding of the benthic communities under investigation.

Table 2.2: The labelset specified for image classification in CoralNET

Short name	Full name	Functional group
Sand	Sand	Abiotic Substrate
Shell Hash	Shell Hash	-
Rocky	Rocky	Abiotic Substrate
Crabaceans	Crabaceans	-
CCA	Caroline Algae	Macroalgae
Halimeda	Halimeda	Macroalgae
Seagrasses	Seagrasses	-
HC	Hard Coral	Hard coral
HC-mas	Massive Hard Coral	Hard coral
SC	Soft Coral	Soft coral
HC-branch	Hard Coral Branching	Hard coral
HC-encr	Encrusting Hard Corals	Hard coral
Dead Coral	Dead Coral	Hard coral
Rubbles	Rubbles	Abiotic Substrate
Al-flesh	Algae	-
Turf	Turf	Abiotic Substrate
SP	Sponges	-

2.6 Data Analysis and Plotting

We managed all the data-related processes using R programming language (R Core Team 2023), which is specifically designed for statistical analysis and creating graphics. We begun by preparing the data, ensuring efficient handling of dates and times with the lubridate package (Grolemund and Wickham 2011). The dplyr package was then used to organize, structure, manipulate, and analyze the data (Wickham et al. 2023). This involved essential tasks like filtering out irrelevant information, sorting the data for efficient analysis, summarizing key findings, and even creating new variables for further insights.

Having prepared the data, we carriout out the spatial dimension with the help of the metR and rgeoda packages (Li and Anselin 2023). These specialized packages enabled to perform advanced analysis and modeling, taking into account the location and spatial relationships within the data. The ggplot2 package was used to create compelling visuals and informative charts that clearly presented the results of our analysis (Wickham 2016). Additionally, the tmap package was uded to map the data geographically (Tennekes 2018), which helped to uncover patterns and relationships that may have otherwise gone unnoticed. Lastly, we integrated text, code, and visualizations using Quarto, which allowed us to create this report. This platform facilitated the organization the findings to ensure that the findings from the analysis are effectively shared to others.

2.7 Code Snippet

```

coralnet.uid = coralnet.tb %>% ①
  mutate(
    label = if_else(
      label %in% c("HC", "C_branch", "HC_encr", "HC_massive",
                  "SC", "D_coral", "Por_branch"),
      "Corals", label)) %>%
  group_by(uid, label) %>% ②
  tally() %>%
  pivot_wider(values_from = n, names_from = label)%>% ③
  mutate(across(everything(), ~replace_na(.x, 0))) %>%
  janitor::adorn_percentages(denominator = "row") %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(across(is.numeric, round, 2)*100, uid = as.integer(uid/100))

wpts.depth.uid = wpts.depth %>% ④
  select(-replicate) %>%
  group_by(uid) %>%
  summarise_all(.funs = median, na.rm = T)

coralnet.uid.pos = coralnet.uid %>% ⑤
  left_join(
    wpts.depth.uid
  ) %>%
  relocate(date:depth, .before = uid) %>%
  arrange(uid) %>%
  ungroup()

coralnet.uid.pos.sf = coralnet.uid.pos %>% ⑥
  filter(!is.na(lat) & lat >= -5.1) %>%
  st_as_sf(coords = c("lon", "lat"), crs = 4326)

```

- ① Take percentage cover dataset from **CoralNet**, and then,
- ② Summarize the percentage cover by grids, and then,
- ③ Convert the summarized dataset from wider to long format, and then,
- ④ Take depth dataset and summarize by grids, and then
- ⑤ Join the percentage cover and depth dataset using `uid` as primary key, then
- ⑥ Create a simple feature dataset from the result of joined dataset.

Chapter 3

Results

3.1 Covered grids

In the benthic ecological survey, a total of 3251 grids were planned for survey from Bagamoyo District in Pwani Region to Mkinga District in Tanga region. These grids cover an estimated area of 3251 square kilometers of coastal shallow water with a maximum depth of 50 meters. But only 3113 grids covering 3113 square kilometers, which is 95.74% of the planned grids were successfully sampled (Figure 3.1). The reason for the other 138 grids that were not sampled is because they overlapped with other grids. These overlapping grids were counted only once, so they were considered duplicates and contributed about 4.26% of the areas we surveyed (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1: The percentage and frequency of the sampled and overlap grids in the surveyed area from Bagamoyo in Pwani Region to Mkinga District in Tanga Region

The overlap occurred because of the way the sampling blocks were generated. During the block creation process, grids touching the boundary lines of multiple blocks were mistakenly counted multiple times. In this case, the grids that touched the boundary lines of the sampling blocks were mistakenly included in the count for each block they touched and instead of being counted just once, they were counted twice. This resulted in an inflated count for some grids, leading to an inaccurate representation of the distribution of data points. To address this issue, the duplicate grids were identified and removed these from the data set. This ensured that each grid was counted only once, providing a more accurate picture of the spatial distribution of data

points within the sampling area.

Originally, we planned for each team to survey 30, 45, and 60 grids every day. However, after taking a closer look at things, we realized that sticking to 30 grids per day was more practical. So, the three teams worked together and surveyed anywhere from 90 to 120 grids each day (Figure 3.2), spreading this effort over a total of 28 days. It’s worth noting that the actual days of sampling fell within the initial plan of 30 to 45 grids per day, as detailed in Table 2.1. This adjustment made the workload more manageable and helped us carried out the survey plan more effectively.

Figure 3.2: The number of grids sampled per day

3.2 Percentage of photo grids

Out of 3113 surveyed areas, we successfully obtained high-quality photos for 2156 (over 69%) grids (Figure 3.3). These photos were uploaded to the CoralNet database for analysis and annotation (Lozada-Misa, Schumacher, and Vargas-Ángel (2017)). Unfortunately, photos are missing for the remaining 957 (about 31%) grids. There were several reasons why photos were not obtained for all grids. In some cases, the grids were located on land, in shallow water, or within small islands, making it impossible to lower the camera to take photos. Additionally, some grids were surveyed in turbid water, resulting in unclear pictures unsuitable for identifying benthic organisms and substrates. Furthermore, some of the grids were located in water deeper than 50 meters. Because it is difficult to find communities of organisms living on the bottom of the sea (benthic communities) at such depths, the camera was not lowered to take pictures. These missing photos represent a significant gap in our understanding of the surveyed area. To address this, further surveys using specialized equipment or techniques may be necessary to capture images from these challenging locations and in turbid water conditions. This will allow for a more complete understanding of the benthic communities and habitats in the area.

Figure 3.3: The frequency and percentage of surveyed grid with and without photos in the surveyed area from Bagamoyo in Pwani Region to Mkinga District in Tanga Region

3.3 Sampling Replicate per grids

Figure 3.4 shows the count and percentage of occurrences for each replicate category. The plot has three segments, each representing a replicate category –Single, Two, and Three replicates, with the size of each segment corresponding to the percentage of coverage. It illustrates the distribution of replicates in the dataset.

Figure 3.4: The percentage and count of replicates in the surveyed grids for the surveyed area from Bagamoyo in Pwani Region to Mkinga District in Tanga Region

The Single replicate category accounts for 1.16% of the entries, while the Two replicate category comprises 1.99%. The majority of the data, 96.85%, corresponds to the Three replicate category, indicating a predominant presence of triple measurements at surveyed locations. A sample of the unique waypoints and corresponding replicates is presented in Table 3.3, which shows data from a benthic ecological survey, detailing various parameters for each recorded entry. Each row corresponds to a specific replicate within a survey grid, with columns indicating the date, longitude, latitude, depth, unique identifier (UID), replicate, and percentages of NODATA, Sand, seagrass, Corals, Rock, and Rubble.

3.4 Benthic Communities

To comprehensively assess benthic community compositions, we divided the selected area into four distinct blocks — Block one, Block two, Block three, and Block four (See Table 3.1). Each block contributed to the overall understanding of the benthic community living on or within the seabed. Benthic samples were collected across all four blocks, aiming for a representative and comprehensive picture of the benthic community within each area. The Table 3.1 illustrates the distribution of samples across the blocks, highlighting the count and percentage for each. As shown in Table 3.1, Block two had the highest number of samples (916), representing 29.51% of the total. Block one followed closely with 885 samples (28.51%), while Block three and Block four contributed 777 (25.03%) and 526 (16.95%) samples, respectively.

Table 3.1: Benthic Sample Distribution across Study Blocks

Blocks	Grid counts	Percentage
Block one	885	28.51
Block two	916	29.51
Block three	777	25.03
Block four	526	16.95
Total	3104	100.00

Furthermore, the benthic ecosystems in each block was assessed, and their percentage composition is presented in Figure 3.5. It covers a diverse range of substrates, encompassing seagrass meadows, vibrant coral reefs, algae beds, rocky outcrops, rubble fields, and expansive sandflats. Additionally, it captures categories for “OTHERS” and “NODATA,” ensuring a complete representation of the benthic landscape.

Figure 3.5: The percentage cover of substrates and benthic habitats within the four sampling blocks

A closer look of Figure 3.5 shows that Block four was dominated with Sand substrates, accounting for 64.74% of the total. Seagrass meadows and coral reefs also contribute significantly, representing 6.17% and 10.35% respectively. Blocks one and three present a distinctive feature,

with sand substrates constituting 66.07% and 72.86% respectively (Table 3.2). However, these blocks consisted of a broader range of substrate types, exhibiting higher percentages and more diverse distributions of seagrass, coral, and other categories. Block two stands out due to its unique composition. Dominated by sand substrates at a staggering 76.64%, it offers a stark contrast to the other blocks (Table 3.2). This high percentage of sand translates to minimal representation of coral reefs and other substrate types, shaping a distinct benthic environment characterized by its expansive sandflats (Table 3.2).

Table 3.2: The percentage cover of substrates and benthic habitats within the four sampling blocks

Block	Benthic communities and Substrates (%)							
	Seagrass	Corals	Algae	Rock	Rubble	Sand	OTHERS	NODATA
Block four	6.17	10.35	8.35	4.18	3.59	64.74	0.19	1.29
Block one	2.87	0.32	1.95	0.29	0.90	66.07	0.10	26.89
Block three	3.15	0.70	0.57	0.29	0.53	72.86	0.01	21.85
Block two	0.04	0.07	1.30	0.01	0.27	76.64	0.08	21.16

The Benthic Ecosystem Survey revealed intriguing patterns in the distribution of various benthic communities, including seagrass meadows, algae, and coral reefs. Notably, the distribution of these benthic communities exhibited striking similarities. For instance, in the block four, which covers the coastal stretch from Tanga to Mkinga seagrass meadows are mainly found in the shallow coastal waters (Figure 3.6), typically at depths below 10 meters (Figure 3.7). On the other hand, algae and coral reefs are more dominant at depths ranging from above 10 meters to below 50 meters (Figure 3.6; Figure 3.7). This differentiation in spatial distribution highlights the specific preferences and ecological niches of these benthic communities in this particular coastal region. The spatial distribution of benthic communities for other block is presented in separate figures. Figure Figure 3.10 illustrates these patterns for block one, while figures Figure 3.11 and Figure 3.12 present them for blocks two and three, respectively.

Figure 3.6: Spatial distribution of seagrass, coral reefs, and algae in Block four

Further analyses of the data (Figure 3.7) reveal a distinct depth-dependent distribution of ben-

thic communities. Seagrass meadows exhibit remarkable dominance in shallow waters, with coverage exceeding 60% below 10 meters. However, their presence rapidly declines to zero at a depth of 15 meters (Figure 3.7). Conversely, coral reefs thrive in moderate depths, with their percentage cover increasing from less than 20% in shallow waters to a peak of approximately 41% at 15 meters depth. Beyond this point, coral cover gradually decreases with increasing depth. Algae communities display a steady increase in coverage with depth, rising from around 15% in shallow waters to a maximum of 28% at a depth of approximately 50 meters (Figure 3.7).

Figure 3.7: The relationship between percentage cover of seagrass, algae and coral reefs with the sampling depth for grids in Block four

3.5 Hotspots and Coldspots Areas of Benthic Communities

The intricate of marine life reveals not only depth-dependent trends but also the presence of distinct clusters with exceptionally high and exceptionally low percentage cover (Figure 3.8). These “hotspots” and “coldspots” represent areas where specific benthic communities thrive or struggle, showcasing the complex interplay of environmental factors and ecological processes. Seagrass meadows: Flourishing meadows with over 60% cover dominate shallow waters, likely due to favorable light penetration and nutrient availability. Abrupt declines in seagrass cover to zero at depths exceeding 15 meters highlight their sensitivity to light limitations and potentially stressful environmental conditions at greater depths.

Figure 3.8: Hotspot areas of high percentage cover for seagrass, coral and algae in the block four

Thriving reefs with cover exceeding 40% are found at moderate depths (Figure 3.8), often characterized by stable water temperature and low sedimentation. Decreasing coral cover beyond moderate depths reflects their vulnerability to factors such as temperature fluctuations and increased sedimentation in deeper waters. Certain areas lack statistically significant patterns for any of the benthic communities (Figure 3.8). These grids might reflect transitional zones between different environmental regimes or areas with high variability in environmental conditions.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusions

The BES study in the northern coast of Tanzania Mainland led to the following conclusions:

- i) The northern coast of Tanzania Mainland features diverse substrates, including seagrass meadows, live coral reefs, algae beds, rocky outcrops, rubbles, and extensive sandflats, with varying proportions of these habitats across different spatial locations;
- ii) Seagrass, algae, and coral reef benthic communities in the northern coast of Tanzania Mainland exhibit a depth-dependent pattern that reveals the unique preferences and biological niches of these communities in this particular coastal area;
- iii) Distinct clusters with notably high and low percentage cover exist along the northern coast of Tanzania Mainland, signifying hotspots and coldspots of seagrass, corals, and algae.

Recommendations

The BES study conducted on the northern coast of Tanzania Mainland resulted in the following recommendations to enhance data collection in future BES studies:

- i) Given the notable 31% of missing photos in the current BES study, which may indicate a substantial knowledge gap in the surveyed area, it is recommended to conduct additional surveys employing specialized equipment or techniques. This would help capture images from challenging locations and under turbid water conditions, ensuring a more comprehensive understanding of the benthic communities and habitats in the region;
- ii) For improved organization in future BES studies, it is recommended to implement block division. This approach has demonstrated effectiveness in monitoring sampling progress and ensuring thorough coverage of the entire survey area;
- iii) For sampling during challenging weather conditions, particularly in rough periods such as the southeast monsoon season, it is recommended to adopt a flexible sampling scenario approach. The three scenarios proposed (sampling 30 grids per day, 45 grids per day, and 60 grids per day) have shown adaptability to varying levels of wind and current strength. Evaluate and adjust daily sampling goals based on current conditions to enhance efficiency.

Acknowledgements

ASUTA extend its heartfelt appreciation to the United Republic of Tanzania for granting us the necessary permissions to conduct the benthic ecological survey in its coastal waters. Without their cooperation and support, this study would not have been possible. A special acknowledgment goes to TAFIRI for providing us with the essential research permit that allowed to carried out this survey. Their cooperation and facilitation significantly contributed to the successful execution of this project.

Lastly, ASUTA express its sincere gratitude to Heshimu Bahari Activity for their invaluable financial and technical support. Their commitment and assistance were instrumental in ensuring the completion of this study. Its contribution not only made the research possible but also enriched the quality and depth of the benthic ecological survey findings. ASUTA is truly grateful for the collaborative efforts that made this study a reality.

Appendix

Table 3.3 represents a subset of a dataset containing information from a benthic ecological survey. Each row corresponds to a specific survey instance, with columns providing details such as the date, longitude, latitude, depth, unique identifier (UId), replicate, and percentages of Nodata, Sand, seagrass, Corals, Rock, Rubble, and Turf.

Table 3.3: A sample of the percentage cover of substrate and habitats of the surveyed grids

	Grid Metadata				Substrate and habitats							
	Lon	Lat	Depth	UId	Replicate	Nodata	Sand	Seagrass	Corals	Rock	Rubble	Algae
1	39.11136	-6.555108	2.5	1	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	39.11273	-6.554446	5.4	1	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	39.11368	-6.553533	3.9	1	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	39.11662	-6.554111	3.1	2	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	39.11770	-6.554880	5.1	2	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	39.11976	-6.554612	6.5	2	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	39.12692	-6.552969	8.2	3	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	39.12729	-6.554705	8.9	3	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	39.12632	-6.552986	7.9	3	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	39.12532	-6.545594	11.9	4	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	39.12744	-6.545371	9.6	4	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	39.12404	-6.544461	8.9	4	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	39.11915	-6.543952	6.9	5	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	39.11793	-6.545400	6.2	5	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	39.11520	-6.544802	6.5	5	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	39.11053	-6.544482	4.4	6	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
17	39.13173	-6.544733	2.8	6	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
18	39.10894	-6.545831	5.0	6	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
19	39.10088	-6.535355	6.9	8	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
20	39.10041	-6.534038	6.7	8	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
21	39.10142	-6.532965	5.4	8	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
22	39.10956	-6.537853	7.6	9	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
23	39.10884	-6.535807	7.6	9	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
24	39.11163	-6.535215	8.1	9	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
25	39.11747	-6.535545	9.6	10	A	56	44	0	0	0	0	0
26	39.11907	-6.535986	9.8	10	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
27	39.12086	-6.535451	10.7	10	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
28	39.12655	-6.534847	10.2	11	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
29	39.12812	-6.536371	11.1	11	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
30	39.12935	-6.536104	15.2	11	C	36	64	0	0	0	0	0
31	39.13569	-6.535466	15.2	12	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
32	39.13729	-6.537101	11.5	12	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
33	39.13975	-6.535114	17.5	12	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
34	39.09532	-6.526559	2.9	13	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
35	39.09450	-6.524813	5.4	13	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
36	39.09389	-6.523380	3.7	13	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
37	39.10155	-6.526898	5.6	14	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
38	39.09972	-6.527546	5.0	14	B	52	48	0	0	0	0	0
39	39.09799	-6.527374	2.9	14	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0

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(continued)

	Lon	Lat	Depth	Uid	Replicate	Nodata	Sand	Seagrass	Corals	Rock	Rubble	Algae
40	39.11064	-6.526868	4.2	15	A	32	68	0	0	0	0	0
41	39.10885	-6.527475	4.9	15	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
42	39.10747	-6.527326	4.6	15	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
43	39.11981	-6.526931	4.3	16	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
44	39.11818	-6.527785	4.7	16	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
45	39.11628	-6.527789	6.5	16	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
46	39.12870	-6.526292	15.1	17	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
47	39.12679	-6.527398	14.3	17	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
48	39.12521	-6.527267	13.2	17	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
49	39.13758	-6.526579	5.5	18	A	0	0	100	0	0	0	0
50	39.13648	-6.527659	7.7	18	B	4	36	60	0	0	0	0
51	39.13431	-6.527498	8.3	18	C	0	72	28	0	0	0	0
52	39.14469	-6.528860	15.3	19	A	0	8	0	4	28	0	60
53	39.14591	-6.526505	26.3	19	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
54	39.14334	-6.526439	6.9	19	C	0	20	0	52	0	4	24
55	39.09269	-6.519981	5.8	20	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
56	39.09112	-6.518253	3.9	20	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
57	39.09294	-6.517923	5.0	20	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
58	39.09853	-6.518144	9.4	21	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
59	39.10039	-6.518529	11.0	21	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
60	39.10211	-6.519053	11.8	21	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
61	39.10760	-6.519397	14.2	22	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
62	39.10949	-6.518516	15.4	22	B	96	4	0	0	0	0	0
63	39.11111	-6.518394	15.4	22	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
64	39.11639	-6.518556	19.0	23	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
65	39.11773	-6.518113	19.1	23	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
66	39.11929	-6.517676	18.1	23	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
67	39.12568	-6.518283	15.5	24	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
68	39.12759	-6.518710	13.7	24	B	12	88	0	0	0	0	0
69	39.12912	-6.518349	13.9	24	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
70	39.13473	-6.518193	2.7	25	A	0	0	100	0	0	0	0
71	39.13660	-6.518514	2.7	25	B	0	0	96	0	0	0	4
72	39.13827	-6.518399	2.5	25	C	0	0	100	0	0	0	0
73	39.14462	-6.516520	29.5	26	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
74	39.14421	-6.517959	31.2	26	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
75	39.14520	-6.515332	34.8	26	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
76	39.08420	-6.509548	2.8	27	A	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
77	39.08276	-6.509057	2.2	27	B	68	32	0	0	0	0	0
78	39.08106	-6.506159	2.5	27	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
79	39.09279	-6.508849	12.9	28	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
80	39.09114	-6.509410	8.7	28	B	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
81	39.08926	-6.510038	7.6	28	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
82	39.10169	-6.510303	18.3	29	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
83	39.09981	-6.509423	17.6	29	B	96	4	0	0	0	0	0
84	39.09766	-6.509063	17.8	29	C	12	84	4	0	0	0	0
85	39.11071	-6.508737	6.7	30	A	12	88	0	0	0	0	0
86	39.10868	-6.509299	6.8	30	B	20	80	0	0	0	0	0
87	39.10679	-6.509300	8.2	30	C	0	0	100	0	0	0	0
88	39.12039	-6.510090	22.5	31	A	4	96	0	0	0	0	0
89	39.11795	-6.508954	28.4	31	B	92	8	0	0	0	0	0
90	39.11570	-6.508834	8.5	31	C	0	96	0	4	0	0	0
91	39.12830	-6.510058	23.8	32	A	0	96	0	0	0	0	4
92	39.12706	-6.510210	24.4	32	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
93	39.12516	-6.510672	22.9	32	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
94	39.13803	-6.509310	33.5	33	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
95	39.13514	-6.509575	29.7	33	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
96	39.12912	-6.508647	27.8	33	C	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
97	39.14549	-6.507476	36.9	34	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
98	39.14541	-6.509400	32.6	34	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
99	39.14573	-6.511483	30.7	34	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
100	39.15239	-6.508916	36.3	35	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0

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(continued)

	Lon	Lat	Depth	Uid	Replicate	Nodata	Sand	Seagrass	Corals	Rock	Rubble	Algae
6276	39.24248	-4.772872	37.4	3186	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6277	39.25271	-4.771104	36.8	3187	A	0	92	0	0	0	0	8
6278	39.25324	-4.772178	31.7	3187	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6279	39.25177	-4.771944	37.3	3187	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6280	39.26390	-4.772025	38.4	3188	A	0	56	0	0	0	0	44
6281	39.26239	-4.772742	39.7	3188	B	0	36	0	0	0	0	64
6282	39.26195	-4.770991	37.7	3188	C	0	40	0	0	0	0	60
6283	39.27148	-4.770919	39.7	3189	A	0	40	0	0	0	0	60
6284	39.27430	-4.772859	39.2	3189	B	0	0	0	0	0	0	100
6285	39.26831	-4.772590	41.5	3189	C	0	12	0	0	0	0	88
6286	39.28188	-4.772303	42.9	3190	A	4	8	0	0	0	0	88
6287	39.27723	-4.777205	37.2	3190	B	0	28	0	0	0	0	72
6288	39.27893	-4.771059	42.5	3190	C	4	24	0	0	0	0	72
6289	39.19143	-4.765050	2.9	3194	A	0	20	60	0	0	0	0
6290	39.19026	-4.763720	3.2	3194	B	0	20	80	0	0	0	0
6291	39.19243	-4.765575	2.7	3194	C	4	52	4	0	0	0	40
6292	39.21678	-4.762045	21.5	3196	A	0	72	0	0	0	0	28
6293	39.21701	-4.763745	23.2	3196	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6294	39.21909	-4.764620	23.3	3196	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6295	39.22467	-4.764164	22.7	3197	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6296	39.22624	-4.763885	23.8	3197	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6297	39.22808	-4.762977	22.1	3197	C	0	96	0	0	0	0	4
6298	39.23345	-4.763779	24.8	3198	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6299	39.23529	-4.763917	23.4	3198	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6300	39.23551	-4.765545	25.1	3198	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6301	39.24303	-4.763760	25.2	3199	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6302	39.24463	-4.763695	26.1	3199	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6303	39.24525	-4.761883	25.9	3199	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6304	39.25205	-4.761978	36.8	3200	A	0	88	0	0	0	0	12
6305	39.25343	-4.763732	33.4	3200	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6306	39.25321	-4.766622	34.4	3200	C	12	88	0	0	0	0	0
6307	39.26115	-4.765293	36.6	3201	A	0	40	0	0	0	0	60
6308	39.26657	-4.766277	35.4	3201	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6309	39.26112	-4.761423	37.7	3201	C	0	88	0	0	0	0	12
6310	39.27275	-4.764969	36.9	3202	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6311	39.27116	-4.763766	31.5	3202	B	0	72	0	0	0	0	28
6312	39.27041	-4.765475	39.2	3202	C	0	44	0	4	0	0	40
6313	39.22018	-4.754185	-	3206	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6314	39.21710	-4.754790	-	3206	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6315	39.21691	-4.756495	-	3206	C	4	0	0	0	0	96	0
6316	39.22810	-4.754577	13.9	3207	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6317	39.22612	-4.754589	21.9	3207	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6318	39.22428	-4.754368	22.7	3207	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6319	39.23414	-4.752114	1.2	3208	A	0	56	0	12	16	0	4
6320	39.23518	-4.754690	3.3	3208	B	0	0	0	100	0	0	0
6321	39.23244	-4.756273	5.1	3208	C	0	0	0	68	0	32	0
6322	39.24439	-4.756516	23.2	3209	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6323	39.24454	-4.754502	22.6	3209	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6324	39.24442	-4.752938	22.9	3209	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6325	39.25194	-4.755685	31.7	3210	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6326	39.26195	-4.756351	32.4	3211	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6327	39.26221	-4.754632	30.7	3211	B	0	52	0	8	0	0	40
6328	39.26055	-4.754034	30.9	3211	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6329	39.21740	-4.743725	15.6	3215	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6330	39.21739	-4.745756	15.7	3215	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6331	39.21912	-4.746168	19.7	3215	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6332	39.22450	-4.745805	19.6	3216	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6333	39.22624	-4.745441	12.1	3216	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6334	39.22788	-4.745357	20.7	3216	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6335	39.23280	-4.745066	20.8	3217	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6336	39.23543	-4.745381	20.2	3217	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0

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	Lon	Lat	Depth	Uid	Replicate	Nodata	Sand	Seagrass	Corals	Rock	Rubble	Algae
6337	39.23495	-4.746916	20.9	3217	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6338	39.24486	-4.747412	24.5	3218	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6339	39.24431	-4.745664	22.6	3218	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6340	39.24618	-4.745325	21.8	3218	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6341	39.25163	-4.744967	22.7	3219	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6342	39.25346	-4.745531	22.4	3219	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6343	39.25239	-4.743743	21.5	3219	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6344	39.21921	-4.735714	16.9	3222	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6345	39.21692	-4.736502	15.7	3222	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6346	39.21701	-4.738330	15.4	3222	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6347	39.22574	-4.734714	17.2	3223	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6348	39.22615	-4.736525	20.1	3223	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6349	39.22450	-4.736133	17.3	3223	C	0	96	0	0	0	0	4
6350	39.23769	-4.737030	20.5	3224	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6351	39.23531	-4.736660	20.1	3224	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6352	39.23468	-4.734695	20.3	3224	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6353	39.24493	-4.738548	20.1	3225	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6354	39.24432	-4.736494	19.9	3225	B	0	96	0	0	0	0	4
6355	39.24253	-4.736102	23.5	3225	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6356	39.21606	-4.728685	3.0	3228	A	0	16	84	0	0	0	0
6357	39.21729	-4.727367	3.9	3228	B	0	4	96	0	0	0	0
6358	39.21732	-4.725578	2.0	3228	C	0	0	100	0	0	0	0
6359	39.22813	-4.726929	18.7	3229	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6360	39.22614	-4.727457	16.4	3229	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6361	39.22632	-4.725633	15.8	3229	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6362	39.23494	-4.729178	16.8	3230	A	4	96	0	0	0	0	0
6363	39.23525	-4.727358	15.5	3230	B	4	96	0	0	0	0	0
6364	39.23348	-4.726995	16.3	3230	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6365	39.21772	-4.718475	2.2	3233	A	0	0	100	0	0	0	0
6366	39.21736	-4.718233	2.5	3233	B	0	0	100	0	0	0	0
6367	39.22727	-4.719926	-	3234	A	0	96	4	0	0	0	0
6368	39.22613	-4.718283	-	3234	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6369	39.22445	-4.718148	-	3234	C	0	96	0	0	4	0	0
6370	39.21604	-4.710721	5.3	3237	A	0	4	96	0	0	0	0
6371	39.21749	-4.709246	5.6	3237	B	0	92	8	0	0	0	0
6372	39.21031	-4.708744	1.7	3237	C	0	60	0	0	0	0	40
6373	39.21831	-4.702021	11.4	3240	A	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6374	39.21723	-4.700127	11.1	3240	B	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
6375	39.21514	-4.700453	10.6	3240	C	0	100	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 3.9: Spatial distribution of Rubble, Sand and Rock in Block four

Figure 3.10: Spatial distribution of seagrass, coral reefs, and algae in Block one along the coastal waters of Bag-amoyo

Figure 3.11: Spatial distribution of seagrass, coral reefs, and algae in Block one along the coastal waters of Bagamoyo and Pangani

Figure 3.12: Spatial distribution of seagrass, coral reefs, and algae in Block one along the coastal waters of Pangani District

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+255 714-880-997

<https://asuta.or.tz>

info@asuta.or.tz

The Benthic Ecosystem Survey, carried out by the Asasi ya Uwezeshaji Tanzania (ASUTA), provided valuable insights into the benthic habitats of the northern Tanzanian coast.

Asasi ya Uwezeshaji Tanzania – ASUTA

Mwanga Tower,
Third Floor, Room No.06
P.O.Box 70030

+255 714-880-997

<https://asuta.or.tz>

info@asuta.or.tz